

PROBABILISTIC ANALYSIS OF WIND TURBINE BLADES CONSIDERING STIFFNESS, STRENGTH AND STABILITY UNDER EXTREME AND FATIGUE LOADING

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Keywords: Uncertainty, Structural design, Probabilistic analysis, Wind turbine rotor blades

ABSTRACT

Optimization of the structural reliability level is in the centre of attention of the engineering community, since it is a driver for the cost efficient design of structures. To successfully achieve this demanding task, various types of uncertainty should be quantified during the design process on a rational way based upon appropriate data. In this work, recently developed probabilistic analysis tools are integrated along with research results relevant to the uncertainty of parameters influencing reliability prediction. Probabilistic analysis is performed based on tools developed earlier for application on wind turbine blades. The methodologies are enhanced by taking into account measurement uncertainty for the material properties replacing the modelling of material inherent variability, which was included in previous analysis, as well as modelling uncertainty. The stochastic nature of the material properties is taken into account by means of the comprehensive OPTIMAT database, while measurement uncertainty on material properties relies on methodologies developed earlier. Modelling uncertainty is estimated through results of a comparative study among 6 organizations within the INNWIND.EU project. The application is performed on the INNWIND.EU reference 10MW wind turbine blade. Failure probability is estimated using crude Monte Carlo simulation against strength under extreme loading, as well as variable amplitude fatigue loading, estimated at the material ply level on several locations on each section of the blade. In addition to that the reliability against buckling is quantified implementing the Response Surface Method combined with Monte Carlo. The effect of the introduced modelling and measurement uncertainty is directly investigated on the failure probability of the rotor blade.

1. INTRODUCTION

Engineering composite structures operate during most of their life under cyclic loading patterns of stochastic nature e.g. wind, sea wave etc. Furthermore, stochastic behaviour arises due to inherent variability (two phases: fibers and matrix) of material properties and manufacturing process of composite materials. The variability on the applied loads, the material properties and the geometrical characteristics of the laminates imply that a number of uncertainties are involved in the design of the composite structure. The rational methods to quantify the effect of these uncertainties on the final design constitute the field of structural reliability.

Privileged area to apply structural reliability principles is the design of composite wind turbine rotor blades. This is because of several challenges encountered in modern wind turbine (WT) blade design, among them their light weight structure in contrast to their extensive up scaling, the demand of continual performance of the rotor blade for its entire design life etc. For the machine of the future i.e. 20MW power output with blade lengths of about 120m, uncertainty quantification and reliability analysis become mandatory to assure an affordable and safe design.

Reliability analyses of rotor blades have already been performed taking into account various type of uncertainties i.e. physical, statistical and model uncertainties on both loads and material properties, assessing the reliability level of existing designs and further calibrating safety factors [1]-[6]. Model uncertainties on the aforementioned works were mainly connected to the aero-elastic load calculations, the material properties when the blade structure was assumed operating on extremely harsh environments as well as the failure criteria associated with the composite materials. These uncertainties were primarily quantified based upon engineering judgement, while appropriate experimental data were used upon availability only for material characteristics. On the other hand, a major source of uncertainty, the measurement uncertainty introduced within the experimental characterization of the composite material was totally ignored.

Herein, a reliability analysis exercise is implemented for the reference 10 MW wind turbine blade developed in the frame of INNWIND.EU project. For the first time, measurement uncertainty is taken into account by applying principles of metrology [7] and based on the methodology presented in [8]. New modelling uncertainties related to the structural analysis models, the applied boundary conditions (i.e. load introduction on the blade model), the estimation of the critical buckling load and the fatigue stress factor calculations are also considered in the light of the benchmark study results within INNWIND.EU project [9]. The benchmark exercise, performed by six organizations (universities and research institutes), involved the extensive comparison on structural blade design tools in terms of displacements, stress-strain components, eigen-frequencies, buckling load factor and damage index. Reliability analysis is executed using recently developed probabilistic analysis tools [2], [6]. The stochastic nature of the material properties is modelled by means of the extensive experimental results in OPTIMAT database [10]. Stochastic representation of extreme loads is performed by applying load extrapolation techniques on 10 min sectional stress resultants time series, available through INNWIND.EU [11]. Failure probability is estimated using crude Monte Carlo simulation under extreme loading, as well as variable amplitude fatigue loading, estimated at the material ply level on several locations on each section of the blade. In addition to that the reliability against buckling is also quantified implementing the Response Surface Method combined with crude Monte Carlo. The effect of the introduced modelling and measurement uncertainty is directly investigated on the failure probability against each of the failure conditions (static, fatigue, buckling) of the rotor blade.

2. ROTOR BLADE

The case study concerned the INNWIND.EU 10 MW reference WT [12], a horizontal, variable speed, collective-pitch controlled wind turbine with a three-bladed upwind rotor. Each blade expands to a length equal to 89.17m and has a nominal mass of 41,788 kg.

The structural design of the blade defined in [12] is based on a load carrying box girder with two shear webs and a cylindrical root. A third shear web is present close to the trailing edge from 21.8m to the tip. The material used is Glass/Epoxy composite and balsa wood sandwich panels. Three glass fabrics of different texture were used, namely a uniaxial, a biaxial with ± 45 fibre orientation and a triaxial with 0 and ± 45 fibre orientation, to form the plies of numerous lamination schemes. Details on the blade geometry and materials are given in [12]. For the purposes of this work, small modifications on the blade design were performed considering each ply of the multidirectional fabrics separately.

3. MATERIAL PROPERTIES

To quantify measurement uncertainty of the material properties, experimental data as well as detailed information about the performance of the tests is needed. The OPTIDAT database [10] constitutes one of the most comprehensive and complete database for Glass/Epoxy materials. Thus, uncertainty quantification is based upon the specific experimental measurements. To clarify, testing results with full information about their testing procedure, for which the authors had complete access, concerned the measurements from one laboratory reported in [13]. Therefore, the outcome of the present statistical analysis can be viewed only as a favourable scenario missing some part of the introduced measurement uncertainty e.g. plate to plate variability (coupons cut from one plate) or laboratory to laboratory variability.

Measurands were the stiffness and the strength properties of the building ply i.e. modulus of elasticity parallel to the fibers, E_1 , transversely, E_2 , Major Poisson ratio, ν_{12} and in-plane shear modulus, G_{12} , the tensile, X_T , and compressive, X_C , strength in the fiber direction, the corresponding transverse ones, Y_T , Y_C and the in-plane shear strength S . Most of the material properties were determined in accordance to relevant ISO standards [13].

The uncertainty analysis was performed based on the principles of GUM [7]. The combined standard uncertainty u_p i.e. the uncertainty of the measurands is thus determined by the uncertainty propagation law given by:

$$u_p^2 = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_j} \right)^2 u_{x_j}^2 + 2 \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \sum_{k=j+1}^n \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_k} u_{x_j} u_{x_k} r(x_j, x_k) \quad (1)$$

where p the quantity determined by combining more than one of the measured (input) quantities x_j , u_{x_j} the standard uncertainty of x_j , f the mathematical model between the measurand p and x_j and r the correlation coefficient between x_j and x_k .

To determine the measurands during the static tests, measurements were performed on specimen thickness and width, the load applied during test and the strains in the axial and/or transverse direction of the coupons. Several sources of uncertainty were taken into account in the uncertainty quantification. That is, uncertainty due to (i) test instruments (load cell, strain gauge, resolution of micrometre and calliper), specimen (dimensions, tolerances) and test procedure (standard's recommendations). The analytical formulation of the combined uncertainty u_p along with the associated input variables x_j for each mesurand can be found in [8].

The main goal, in the current exercise is to quantify uncertainty on the statistical characteristics i.e.

sample mean value, $E(p) = \mu_p = \frac{\sum p_i}{n}$, and variance, $Var(p) = s_p^2 = \frac{\sum (p_i - \mu_p)^2}{n-1}$, of each material property due to the aforementioned sources of uncertainties with n being the number of tests performed for every property. Following [7], [14], the combined uncertainty on the mean can be derived by Eq. (1) and is given by:

$$u_c^2(\mu_p) = \frac{s_p^2}{n} + (u_p^2 - s_p^2) \quad (2)$$

where u_p is the standard uncertainty estimated by Eq. (1). Because for a given property e.g. X_T every single measurement p_i results in different u_p value, thus, in Eq. (2)-(3), the average value of the combined standard uncertainty of the measurand is further used. In a similar approach, the combined uncertainty on the variance can be found to be:

$$u_c^2(s_p^2) = \frac{4s_p^2 u_p^2}{n-1} + \frac{8(u_p^2 - s_p^2)}{(n-1)^2} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n (p_i - \mu_p)(p_j - \mu_p) \quad (3)$$

Applying Eq. (2)-(3) on the OPTIDAT experimental data, the coefficient of variation (CoV), i.e. the ratio of the standard deviation over the mean value, of the mean value, $CoV(\mu_p)$, and the standard deviation $CoV(s_p)$ of each property is determined. Results are reported in Table 1 under the heading Propagation Law. The mean values of the stiffness and strength properties (μ_p) as retrieved by [12] and the coefficient of variation of each property ($CoV(p)$) as determined through the OPTIDAT database, are also shown in Table 1, under the heading Data.

Usually, physical uncertainty of the basic variables is taken into account by inserting only the statistics of experimental data, μ_p and $CoV(p)$ of Table 1 into the reliability calculations. Taking into account the statistics under the heading Propagation law of Table 1, physical, statistical and measurement uncertainty are considered in reliability calculations. On the contrary, by taking advantage of the asymptotic properties of the maximum likelihood estimators (ap-MLE) for the mean and standard deviation of the experimental data, as explicitly described in [3], only the physical and statistical uncertainty is taken into account. Results of the methodology described in [3] are shown in Table 1 under the heading ap-MLE.

Property (p)		Data		Propagation Law		ap-MLE	
		μ_p	CoV(p)	CoV(μ_p)	CoV(s_p)	CoV(μ_p)	CoV(s_p)
E_1	[GPa]	41.63	2.73%	0.97%	19.44%	0.51%	13.36%
E_2	[GPa]	14.93	2.31%	1.72%	20.41%	0.45%	14.14%
ν_{12}		0.24	9.16%	9.08%	19.85%	1.76%	13.36%
G_{12}	[GPa]	5.05	2.38%	2.32%	21.20%	0.49%	14.74%
X_T	[MPa]	941.53	3.65%	0.82%	19.25%	0.81%	13.36%
X_C	[MPa]	665.75	3.11%	0.80%	21.82%	0.55%	15.08%
Y_T	[MPa]	81.58	4.78%	3.56%	20.41%	0.94%	14.14%
Y_C	[MPa]	200.6	2.95%	1.11%	10.00%	0.57%	13.87%
S	[MPa]	58.59	1.83%	1.80%	21.32%	0.37%	14.74%

Table 1: Statistics for the material properties determined by (i) the uncertainty propagation law (ii) the asymptotic properties of the MLE.

In line with JCSS [15], all the material properties were assumed to follow the lognormal distribution (LN). Correlation between the properties is taken into account. Part of the correlation matrix was derived directly from the available OPTIDAT data. Only five from the thirty six required correlation coefficients were possible to be evaluated ($\rho_{E_1-\nu_{12}}=0.21$, $\rho_{E_1-X_T}=-0.55$, $\rho_{E_2-Y_T}=-0.04$, $\rho_{\nu_{12}-X_T}=0.15$, $\rho_{G_{12}-S}=-0.24$). The remaining ones were assigned a low correlation value, equal to 0.1, ensuring a positive semi definite matrix. Depending on the property, the uncertainty for the mean values including measurement uncertainty, evaluated by the propagation law, can be much higher compared against the respective one when only statistical uncertainty is taken into account, implementing the ap-MLE method e.g. for ν_{12} , G_{12} , Y_T . The same holds true for the uncertainty of the standard deviation of each property.

To estimate the cumulative distribution function (CDF) introducing the quantified statistical and measurement uncertainty, a simulation procedure was implemented as presented in [5]. That is, assuming that μ_p , s_p are normally distributed random variables with mean values as indicated in Table 1 under the heading Data and CoV values given either under the heading Propagation Law or under the heading ap-MLE depending on whether measurement uncertainty is considered or not, N_B sample points are generated for the mean value and standard deviation of each property. Further, Lognormal parameters are estimated for every set of μ_p , s_p following basic statistical theory. Eventually, samples of size N_f for the property are generated for each set of the Lognormal parameter values while the correlation matrix of the material properties is also taken into account. Random number generation for non-normal correlated random variables are discussed in section 5. The derived sample ($N_B * N_f$) is considered to be representative for the physical, statistical and/or measurement uncertainty. An example for the empirical CDFs considering the various types of uncertainty can be seen in Fig. 1a and b for the tensile strength in the fiber direction (X_T) and the shear strength (S), respectively.

Fig. 1: a) Tensile strength in the fiber direction and b) shear strength considering various types of uncertainty

Empirical distribution was estimated by sorting the simulated data of each material property in ascending order and assigning a specific probability value ($P_i=i/(n+1)$) to every sorted value in the sample. An extra curve representing the lower 95% confidence level (LCL) for the mean value that GL [16] suggests when estimating characteristic values, is also superimposed in Fig. 1.

The various types of uncertainty mainly affect the tails of the distribution. In all cases, the more uncertainty components are included (physical, statistical, measurement) the more to the left is the left (lower) tail of the CDF curves moved, as shown in Fig. 1. When measurement uncertainty is taken into account and in the case that the mean value of the property exhibits a $\text{CoV}(\mu_p)$ value above a threshold (approximately 1%), the results are more conservative compared against the LCL (95%) curve, e.g. as depicted for the shear strength, S , in Fig. 1b. Yet, this is not the case for e.g. the strength in tension along the fibre direction (X_T), shown in Fig. 1a.

4. LOADS

The strength of the blade and elastic stability under extreme loading were examined for the power production state of the wind turbine, DLC 1.1, implementing the Normal Turbulence Model for various wind speed bins in the interval $[V_{\text{in}}, V_{\text{out}}]$ of cut-in and cut-out wind speeds. More specifically, one 10 minute time series of stress resultants at various cross-sections along the blade length for twelve different wind-speed bins were provided in the frame of the INNWIND.EU project by Politecnico di Milano [11]. Despite of the single seed simulation for the time series, these were further processed to represent the stochastic extreme loading for the objective of the present work.

Load extrapolation was performed on the sectional stress resultants time series namely the flap and edgewise bending moments, the respective shear forces and the torsional moment following IEC 61400-1 ed.3 [17]. Axial force is mainly dictated by gravitational and centrifugal forces and thus it was considered as a deterministic variable. Local maxima were extracted from the 10 min simulations adopting the peak over threshold method. The threshold value was set according to IEC proposal i.e. equal to the mean value plus 1.4 standard deviation of the time series for each wind speed bin. A time separation of 10 seconds was also imposed to ensure statistical independence between successive maxima. The 3p-Weibull was selected to fit local maxima for all the wind speed bins. The long-term exceedance probability of the extreme sectional stress resultants for the 10 min and 1 year reference period (T) was estimated following the formulation in [17] and [6] respectively. Correlation between extreme stress resultants was also taken into account assuming fully correlated bending moments and shear forces in the flap and edge direction respectively. As an example, the exceedance probability for the extreme edgewise bending moment for $T=1$ yr. is shown in Fig. 2. The load values have been normalized with respect to the maximum load value from all provided simulations.

Due to the limited number of available time series, statistical uncertainty was taken into account. The Bootstrap technique was used to quantify the uncertainty exactly as described in [5]. Moreover, model uncertainties related to the aero-elastic load calculations, introduced in [3], were also considered in the present analysis. That is, model uncertainties related to the dynamic response of the WT, the terrain roughness, the landscape topography, the lift and drag coefficients, the stress calculations from wind load as well as statistical uncertainty due to limited amount of wind data. For the extreme edge moment stress resultants, the annual long-term exceedance probabilities can be seen in Fig. 2 considering all types of uncertainty. The characteristic value with a recurrence period of 50 yrs. as IEC standard suggests is also depicted in Fig. 2. It is very interesting to notice the great influence of the model uncertainties of [3] to the annual distribution of the extremes. The CoV values for the annual loads considering all uncertainty types were estimated between 26-30% when the respective ones considering only physical uncertainty are 4-7%.

Concerning the analysis under variable amplitude loading, the parked condition of the wind turbine, DLC 6.4, was also considered additionally to DLC 1.1. A Rayleigh distribution was assumed for the wind speed with the average wind speed at the site equal to 10m/s. For the purpose of this work and because the probability of failure with the original fatigue load envelope for 20 years of operational life was insignificant, the number of occurrence for every 10 min simulation in the various wind speed bins was considerably increased.

Fig. 2: Empirical plot for the long-term exceedance probability of the extreme edge bending moment considering all uncertainty types at the section with the maximum chord

5. PROBABILISTIC TOOL

The probabilistic analysis was performed using PROBUST [6], a dedicated tool for the reliability and structural analysis of composite rotor blade sections under ultimate loading. The tool is operating in MATLAB environment by modifying FORTRAN subroutines of THIN [2] and CUFISM [18] into Matlab Executable as well as developing new source code. In the present work, the code was enhanced with an extra module capable to perform structural analysis for variable amplitude loading at the ply level of the blade section.

PROBUST consists of four distinct processes. The first process concerns the stochastic representation of the basic variables i.e. the in-plane thermo-mechanical properties of the unidirectional composite ply, the ply thickness, the developed sectional stress resultants as well as the gradient of operating and curing temperature and the moisture content.

The second process concerns the structural analysis of the rotor blade. The program can be used for stress and instability analysis in multi-cellular orthotropic beam sections using thin wall theory and finite strip method (FSM) respectively. Additionally, fatigue analysis is performed adopting the modified Goodman diagram according to GL [15] and implementing the rainflow counting method. Thus, the number of tolerable load cycles N is given by

$$N = \left[\frac{R_{k,t} + |R_{k,c}| - |2\gamma_{Ma} S_{k,M} - R_{k,t} + |R_{k,c}|}{2(\gamma_{Mb}/C_{1b}) S_{k,A}} \right]^m \quad (4)$$

where $R_{k,t}$, $R_{k,c}$ are the characteristic short-term structural member resistance for tension and compression, S_{kA} , S_{kM} denote the amplitude and mean value of the characteristic actions, m equals 10 for Glass/epoxy composites, γ_{Ma} , γ_{Mb} material safety factors for extreme and fatigue analysis and C_{1B} is $N^{1/m}$. The Palmgren-Miner damage index (D) is finally calculated at the ply level of the composite structure. It should be mentioned that only the axial stresses are taken into account in the FSM and fatigue calculations presented herein.

In the third process, the limit state function is determined. For the strength analysis under ultimate loading, the limit state function is given by

$$g(\mathbf{X}) = X_R f_1(\mathbf{X}, X_D) - 1 \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{X} the vector of the basic variables, $f_1(\mathbf{X})$ a function expressing the strength ratio i.e. the ratio of allowable stress over the applied one, according to each failure criterion, X_R a random variable quantifying the model uncertainty related to the adopted failure criterion and X_D a random variable expressing the model uncertainty related to the structural model used to evaluate deflections. For the elastic stability, the limit state function is described by

$$g(\mathbf{X}) = X_{\lambda} \lambda_1 - 1 \quad (6)$$

where λ_1 the critical eigenvalue and X_{λ} a random variable quantifying the model uncertainty related to the evaluation of the load factor. For the fatigue analysis, the limit state function is expressed in terms of the fatigue stress factor (FSF) defined as $FSF = D^{-1/m}$ with D the Palmgren-Miner damage index and m the slope parameter of the S/N curve introduced in Eq. (4). The limit state function is then given by

$$g(\mathbf{X}) = X_{FSF} FSF - 1 \quad (7)$$

where defined by, X_{FSF} is a random variable quantifying the model uncertainty related to the calculation of the fatigue stress factor. In all three cases, limit state function values greater than zero, $g(\mathbf{X}) > 0$, correspond to safe mode.

The fourth process in PROBUST implements probabilistic methods for reliability estimation. In the current exercise, the crude Monte Carlo (MC) method was used for strength analysis under ultimate and variable amplitude loading. Sample values for every random variable were formed and repetitive simulations were performed. The failure probability (P_f) for every ply is estimated as the ratio of the number of failures to the total number of simulations. A major issue of concern in implementing the MC method is the random number generators. For correlated non-normal variables, the NORTA method was implemented as described in [19] by adopting the formulation developed in [20]. For instability investigations, the Response Surface Method (RSM) combined with crude MC was followed. The RSM implementation is according to the approach A0 presented in [21]. A suitable regression model for the mechanical model was built to further perform crude Monte Carlo simulation. A detailed description of both MC and RSM_A0/MC method as well as their implementation can be found in [6].

6. MODEL UNCERTAINTY

The work performed within the INNWIND.EU project provides the baseline for the estimation of model uncertainty [11]. Six organizations participated in the benchmark on structural analysis tools for wind turbine blades. As all partners were supported with the same information regarding the blade external structure, the internal material lay-out as well as loading that should be imposed on the blade it was possible to compare the output and assess the variability of the results. The results were derived by each partner using their own tools (fully in-house developed or combined with commercially available ones), with its specific structural analysis approach (thin wall theory and finite element (FE) models using beam, shell or solid elements) and their preferable analysis type (linear or geometrical non-linear). It is recognized that neither the accuracy nor the correctness of the numerical simulation results can be assessed, since for that purpose comparison against experimental data should be available. Yet, given the capability of the participants in the benchmark study on structural analysis and their experience in comparing numerical simulation results of wind turbine blades against data, the relevance of the results is evident. Therefore, it becomes possible to quantify model uncertainty introduced in Eq. (4)-(6).

Concerning the deflection and critical load factor evaluations, two different sources of uncertainty are present. The first one concerned uncertainty due to the structural model i.e. structural analysis theory employed by each partner e.g. the beam Bernoulli theory and FSM for PROBUST stiffness and buckling evaluations respectively. The second source of uncertainty is related to the boundary condition applied to the model, or simply put how the loads are introduced on the structural model. Extensive comparison was performed for the 10 MW reference blade computing deflections along the blade length as well as critical eigenvalues of the whole blade [11]. For the section of interest i.e. the section with the maximum chord, coefficient of variations of the respective model uncertainties X_D and X_{λ} were estimated and are shown in Table 2. The mean values were assumed to be equal to unity. It should be mentioned that the performance with a specific structural analysis tool, herein PROBUST, could possible introduce bias in the variables of Table 2 resulting in mean values other than unity. That would be the case of e.g. PROBUST computations to be always more conservative or non-

conservative in relation to the other tools. This, however, was not further investigated in the current application.

Model uncertainty related to the evaluation of fatigue stress factor was also quantified in the benchmark exercise [11]. The various sources of uncertainty include the structural model, the calculation method of the stresses, the rainflow counting method (including parameters such as the bin size), the calculation of the damage from a pair of stress mean and amplitude and the load modelling. Mean value and coefficient of variation for X_{FSF} can be seen in Table 2 for two cases. In the first case, the uncertainty was quantified based on partners' results derived by structural analysis tools similar to PROBUST i.e. sectional analysis tools. For the second case, all results were included in the uncertainty estimation. The effect is quite strong. It should be mentioned that uncertainty due to the employed constant life diagrams and due to the considered damage index estimation is not taken into account. Thus, model uncertainty, X_{FSF} , introduced in the present work should be considered as a favourable case.

Work on the quantification of the model uncertainty related to failure criteria of composite materials, X_R , has already been performed in [4] based on appropriate experimental data. Results were adopted herein. For completeness, the statistics of X_R are also presented in Table 2.

According to JCSS, model uncertainty is characterized by a Normal distribution. Due to the large CoV value however e.g. in case of X_R , negative values may be introduced and thus quantities that should always be positive become negative ones e.g. the strength ratio f_i of Eq. (5). To circumvent the difficulty a Lognormal distribution is selected for these cases.

	mean	CoV	Distr	Ref
X_R	1.14	0.300	LN	[4]
X_D	1.00	0.038	N	
X_λ	1.00	0.229	LN	[11]
X_{FSF}	1.00	0.050	N	
	1.00	0.340	LN	

Table 2: Model uncertainties related to stiffness calculations, load introduction, failure criterion, critical eigenvalue and fatigue stress factor estimation

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to [9], the critical section of the blade was found to be close to the maximum chord section. Therefore, reliability analysis for the section at the maximum chord of the 10 MW reference blade was performed considering the strength under extreme and variable loading as well as the elastic stability.

For strength analysis under extreme loading, random variables were considered the stiffness and strength properties as well as the extreme stress resultants presented in section 3 and 4 respectively. Crude Monte Carlo simulations were executed for a sample size of $2E+06$. The effect of taking into account the various types of uncertainty for the material properties presented in section 3 on the annual β index of the blade can be seen in Fig. 3. It should be mentioned that the β index is related to the failure probability by $P_f = \Phi(-\beta)$, with $\Phi()$ the normal distribution. The analyzed section consists of 136 2-node laminated elements with 9 plies per element. Assuming first ply failure for each laminated element, the minimum β value for every lamination scheme, i.e. the worst case of all plies in the element, is depicted in Fig. 3. Due to the sample size of $2E+06$, a lower bound in the estimated probability of $P_f = 5E-07$ ($\beta = 4.89$) is implied. Results of Fig. 3 concern the implementation of the Tsai-Wu failure criterion [22] with cross term given by $F_{12} = -0.5\sqrt{F_{11}F_{22}}$ while the labels ‘‘Mat(P)’’, ‘‘Mat(P+S)’’, ‘‘Mat(P+S+M)’’ correspond to physical, statistical and measurement uncertainty on the material properties respectively. Model uncertainties related to the extreme loads as well as uncertainties presented in Table 2 are not included in results of Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Effect of various types of uncertainty related to material properties at the blade section (T=1 yr.)

Generally, the influence of the measurement uncertainty on the β values of Fig. 3 is minor. It is more pronounced in the low β values i.e. the higher probability of failure values; see e.g. elements 65-68 in the suction side of the nose (leading edge) of the section. This was expected considering that the introduction of the measurement uncertainty leads to higher, but comparable variation of the mean and standard deviation of the material, as depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 4: Effect of various types of model uncertainty at the blade section (T=1 yr.)

On the other hand, introducing the model uncertainties of the loads, the β index values decrease considerably; see the curve with the label “Load model unc” in Fig. 4. Adding further the model uncertainty related to the structural modelling and load introduction, X_D , the β values are slightly reduced. Introducing, however, the uncertainty on the failure criterion, X_R , the effect becomes considerably larger. Same effect was found using the Puck failure criterion, which indicates that initialization of matrix cracks in the $[\pm 45]$ plies is the driving failure mode.

For the elastic stability analysis, stiffness properties as well as flap and edge bending moments were considered random variables. The RSM_A0/MC was implemented executing 2,000,000 simulations. Two iterations of the RSM approach [21] were proved to yield quite satisfactory results.

The effect of taking into account the various types of uncertainty (physical, statistical and measurement) for the material properties as well as model uncertainties related to the loads and the

eigenvalue calculations X_2 , introduced in Table 2 on the annual β index of the blade section is presented in Table 5.

cases	β index	P_f
Mat(P)	1.348	8.9E-02
Mat(P+S)	1.344	8.9E-02
Mat(P+S+M)	1.331	9.2E-02
Load model unc	0.711	2.4E-01
Load model unc+ X_2	0.481	3.2E-01

Table 3: Annual β index and P_f for elastic instability considering the various types of uncertainty

The influence of the measurement uncertainty is quite limited in the studied case. This is not the case when model uncertainties are introduced to the reliability calculations. However, it should be emphasized that the material dataset used in the present example consists of a rather large set (30 specimens per property) from a single plate having in most cases a very low coefficient of variation $CoV(p)$, in contrary to what is generally required by the certification bodies (7 specimens according to GL and 7 specimens from 3 plates according to DNV).

For fatigue analysis followed the static strengths were taken into account as random variables (see Eq. 4). Due to the ply level approach, a vast amount of calculations are performed transforming sectional stress resultants to stresses at the layer for every record in the time series. The MC method was executed for 1,000,000 sample values, which implies lower bound in the estimated probability equal to $P_f=1E-06$ ($\beta=4.75$)

The influence of taking into account two different values for the model uncertainty X_{FSF} of Table 2, on the β value at multiple locations of a blade section can be seen in Fig. 5. Fig. 5 reveals the great influence of the uncertainty on structural analysis theories results on the fatigue reliability estimations of the blade structure.

Fig. 5: Effect of model uncertainty X_{FSF} at the blade section

By quantifying the individual uncertainty sources incorporated into the design of the blade, one gets a clearer picture of those (epistemic ones) that should be reduced by additional effort, so that the target reliability level is maintained and the use of materials optimized on the structure. In the cases presented, the methodology on the measurement uncertainty provides insight on the material properties side. Improvements on the experimental method followed for the properties characterisation, reducing the uncertainty, will directly show on the reliability estimations. On the simulation side, there is a dominant effect by the uncertainty of the loads. Yet, the uncertainty estimation for the loads are based on engineering judgement, rather than data and information of structural codes not depicting the sophisticated wind modelling performed in wind energy applications. On the other hand, the introduction of uncertainty for the failure model (failure criterion) of the composite material is shown to introduce also a high uncertainty at the final result. The value

for this uncertainty, nevertheless, was defined in [4] by experimental data, revealing the need to improve modelling for composite materials. Further to that, the model uncertainty considered for the fatigue case, although not including the uncertainty in failure prediction by the limit criterion was found similarly significant.

8. CONCLUSIONS

Herein, the combined uncertainty for the statistical characteristics i.e. sample mean and standard deviation of each material property of a composite ply was formulated including measurement, statistical, physical uncertainty sources and was further quantified. Uncertainty analysis performed according to the principles of metrology using the OPTIDAT database. Variability on the sample mean was found to fluctuate between 0.8-10%. For the standard deviation, the CoV values were much higher and equal to 19-22%. Measurement uncertainty affects mainly the tails of the distribution of the material property while, depending on the CoV value of the sample mean, it could have a more pronounced effect on these.

Model uncertainties related to the aero-elastic load calculations were adopted from literature. Their effect on the annual exceedance distribution of the stress resultants proved to be quite significant, yielding CoV values of even 26-30%. Model uncertainties related to the structural blade model and the boundary conditions (load introduction) on the model were also quantified in the light of the results of INNWIND.EU project for analysis under extreme loading (static and buckling), as well as under variable loading (fatigue). These values were further taken into account in the reliability calculations.

As an example, reliability analysis of the 10 MW reference blade (90m Glass/Epoxy) was performed considering three analysis types (strength under ultimate and variable amplitude loading and elastic stability) introducing the measurement uncertainty in the material properties, the aforementioned model uncertainties as well as model uncertainties related to the failure criterion regarding strength estimations. Due to the specific blade design and the load cases considered, reliability calculations on the section with the maximum chord yield quite low β values especially for the buckling analysis. For the strength analysis under ultimate load (static) low β values were largely connected with the initiations of matrix cracks on the $[\pm 45]$ plies.

In the example case studied and noting that to incorporate material uncertainty a benign database was used, the largest influence on the reliability prediction is introduced through model uncertainties. Especially, the uncertainty of the failure criterion, as well as the uncertainty for the loads, the latter primarily driven by uncertainties in the model to define the extreme loads, have a significant impact on the probability of failure. Further work should be performed in order to rationalize the uncertainties introduced and wherever possible reduce them. This could be performed through experimental investigations where information is currently not available (e.g. loads). Especially for the uncertainty in loads, the values based on engineering judgement from standardization committees, date back to 2000. Since then, a lot of improvements have been introduced in the simulation for wind turbines. Therefore, revisiting those values is recommended.

Finally introduction of the uncertainty in the fatigue failure model for the composite materials, which is comparable or even higher than that for the static case, will have a strong effect on the reliability results. Improving failure models for composites and thereby reducing the uncertainties will have a positive impact on the blade design.

9. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Seventh Framework Programme FP7-ENERGY-2013-1-2STAGE under grant agreement No. 609795 (IRPWIND).

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